

APPENDIX 1: Projects	Disciplinary background, approach, and key publications
<p>Climate CAMPAIGNers (2021-2024)</p> <p>This project engaged citizens in real-life experiences with low-carbon behaviours in various domains (e.g. mobility, energy, food, clothing, etc.) via a newly developed smartphone app. Target behaviours are suggested as near-term goals, called #LifestyleChallenges. These are formulated through co-creation with app users, behavioral scientists, and city/regional officials to be impactful and relevant in their area. Following a #LC, the citizens' experience (collected via questionnaire and app data), and achieved CO2 savings are evaluated and made available via an open-source Dashboard Monitor. The key objective is to support the transition of lifestyles to meet the decarbonisation targets of the Paris Agreement.</p> <p>Countries: Ireland, Norway, South Africa, Austria, Canada, Germany, Greece, Italy, Norway, Switzerland, Türkiye, Finland, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Lithuania, France, Sweden, Peru</p>	<p>Partner institutions: Energieinstitut , Johannes Kepler Universität Linz (EI-JKU), National University of Ireland Galway (NUIG), Norges Teknisk-Naturvitenskapelige Universitet (NTNU), University of Cape Town (UCT), Potsdam Institut für Klimafolgenforschung (PIK), Fondazione Eni Enrico Mattei (FEEM), Izmir Ekonomi Universitesi (IUE), Lappeenranta-Lahden Teknillinen Yliopisto (LUT), Baku Engineering University (BEU), Climate Action Network Europe (CANE), ICLEI European Secretariat (ICLEI), European Network for Community-led Initiatives on Climate Change and Sustainability (ECOLISE), SB Konzept GmbH (SBK), E3-Modelling (E3M), Saints GmbH (Saints), Comune di Milano (MILAN), Izmir Buyuksehir Belediyesi (IZMIR), Lahden Kaupunki (LAHTI), Diktyo Aeforikon Nison Toy Aigaiou (DAFNI), Stadt Linz (LINZ), Municipality of Skopelos (SKOPELOS), Stadtgemeinde Freistadt (FREISTADT), Vilnius City Municipality (VILNIUS), Comune di Pesaro (PESARO), Commune de Grenoble (GRENOBLE), State Committee on Urban Planning and Architecture (BAKU), Dublin City Council (DUBLIN), Urbanisland AB (MALMÖ), Gobierno Regional La Libertad, Peru (LIBERTAD).</p> <p>Disciplines: Economics, Geography, Psychology, Sociology, Political Science, Physics, IT, Law, Energy and Industrial Engineering and Management.</p> <p>Quantified foci/approaches on structures: The impact of target behaviours on citizens' emissions (D2.1, D2.2) and related barriers and enablers (surveyed via the app, D5.2). Developing new 'lifestyle-related' climate mitigation pathways which incorporate behavioural change of consumers in mobility and residential goods and services, quantified with the leading energy-system and integrated-assessment models participating in the consortium (PRIMES, REMIND, EDGE, PROMETHEUS, GEM-E3); see D6.1 and D6.2</p> <p>Key publications: Andreou, A., Fragkos, P., Fotiou, T., Filippidou, F. (2022). Assessing lifestyle transformations and their systemic effects in energy-system and integrated assessment models: a review of current methods and data. <i>Energies</i>, 15(14), 4948. Claudelin, A., Tuominen, K., & Vanhamäki, S. (2022). Sustainability perspectives of the sharing economy: Process of creating a library of things in Finland. <i>Sustainability</i>, 14(11), 6627. Guivarch, C., Le Gallic, T., Bauer, N., Fragkos, P., Huppmann, D., Jaxa-Rozen, M., ... & Wagner, F. (2022). Using large ensembles of climate change mitigation scenarios for robust insights. <i>Nature Climate Change</i>, 12(5), 428-435.</p>

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<p>DIALOGUES (May 2021-April 2024)</p> <p>Support the objectives of the Energy Union by operationalizing the concept of ‘energy citizenship’, understood as the ways in which citizens can be enabled to play a central role in the uptake of low-carbon energy solutions.</p> <p>Countries: Austria, Canada, Germany, Greece, Italy, Norway, Switzerland and Turkey.</p>	<p>Partner institutions: Energieinstitut an der Johannes Kepler Universitat Linz Verein (EI JKU), Alleanza per il Clima Italia (CAI), GenderCC-Women for Climate Justice EV (GenderCC), Diktyo Aeforikon Nison toy Aigaiou (DAFNI), Center for the Study of Democracy (CSD), Izmir Ekonomi Universitesi (IUE), Universite de Geneve (UNIGE), Potsdam Institut fuer Klimafolgenforschung (PIK), NTNU Samfunnsforskning AS (NSR), Norges Teknisk-Naturvitenskapelige Universitet NTNU (NTNU), Universita degli Studi Roma Tre (UNIROMA3), Globaz, S.A. (LOBA), Universite du Quebec a Montreal*UQAM (UQAM)</p> <p>Disciplines: Anthropology, sociology, economics, energy economics, gender studies, political science, political economy, environmental psychology, social psychology, engineering, geography, law, public policy and administration</p> <p>Quantified foci/approaches on structures: Decision Support Tool (D8.3), Energy Citizenship Scale (D2.3) used in a survey among 700 participants. A meta-analysis of existing data related to energy citizenship (T4.2). Online assessment tool for energy citizenship (D5.1). Pathways to deepening energy citizenship (D5.4), Pre and Post Citizen Action Lab (CAL) survey. Gender as a cross-cutting topic.</p> <p>Key publications: Biresselioglu, M.E., Demir, M.H., Solak, B., Turan, U., 'Understanding the dynamics and conceptualization of environmental citizenship and energy citizenship: Evidence from the existing literature', <i>Frontiers in Energy Research</i>, vol. 10, 20 December 2022, https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2022.1018035. Epp, J., Demir, M., Liste, L., Nilsen, B., Zhan, M., Walter, C., & Sahakian, M. 'Scaling up living lab research through inclusivity and diversity', <i>Sustainability Science, Policy and Practice</i> (under review). Sahakian, M, Zhan, M, Epp, M et al 'Practicing radical imaginaries: the role of action labs for collective energy citizenship', <i>Consumption and society</i> (under review).</p>

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<p>ENCHANT (2020-2023) – Energy Efficiency through behaviour Change Transition –</p> <p>ENCHANT was a project that aimed to support the energy transition by testing the impact of interventions affecting energy consumption behaviour on a large-scale across Europe. The interventions were developed, fitted, and tested with the objective to unlock an energy efficiency potential in the public, through behavioural change.</p> <p>Countries: Austria, Germany, Italy, Norway, Romania, Türkiye.</p>	<p>Partners: Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Energieinstitut an der Johannes Kepler Universität Linz (EI-JKU), University Roma 3 (ROMA3), Universitatea Babeş-Bolyai (UBB), Izmir Economic University (IEU), Smart Innovation Norway (SIN), NTNU Social Research (NSR), Izmir Metropolitan Municipality (IMM), Gediz (GEDIZ), Energie Kompass (EK), Friends of the Earth Norway (NVV), Viken Country (VIKEN), Fondazione Roffredo Caetani (FONDA), Energia Positiva (EP), Electrica (EL), Cluj-Napoca municipality (CNM), Centrul Pentru Studiul Democratiei (CSD), badenova (BDN).</p> <p>Disciplines: Anthropology, Data Modelling & Science, Economics, Geography, Psychology, Sociology.</p> <p>Quantified foci/approaches on structures: The focus was on identifying structural, cultural and individual drivers and barriers to behaviour change in energy use and to intervene with tested and targeted interventions to foster lifestyle change. ENCHANT implemented 15 pilots and captured the structural influence in different ways. In one large pilot in three countries, an online intervention platform was created to lead 2500 participants through a six weeks intervention program to reduce electricity consumption in private households. The structural impact was quantified in several ways in this pilot: (a) weather influence on electricity consumption for heating, cooling, and warming water was tested by accessing weather data (heating degree days and cooling degree days) for the location of each household from a global database. (b) influence of electricity prices on consumption was tested by accessing local electricity prices on a daily basis from a European database of electricity prices. (c) influence of available technical equipment was captured by a survey where people answered which major electricity consuming devices they own. (d) influence of the electricity market structure was captured by comparing the same interventions in three different countries.</p> <p>Key Publications: Klößner, C., Asgarabad, M., Biresselioglu, M., Caffaro, F., Carrus, G., Demir, M., ... & Vesely, S. (2024). Advancing realistic estimations of behaviour interventions: A large-scale real-world experiment on electricity consumption reduction in Europe. www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-3964680/v1 Habibi Asgarabad, M., Vesely, S., Efe Biresselioglu, M., Caffaro, F., Carrus, G., Hakan Demir, M., ... & Klößner, C. A. (2024). Promoting electricity conservation through behavior change: A study protocol for a web-based multiple-arm parallel randomized controlled trial. <i>PLoS one</i>, 19(3), e0293683.</p>

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<p>EnergyPROSPECTS (May 2021 - April 2024)</p> <p>EnergyPROSPECTS (PROactive Strategies and Policies for Energy Citizenship Transformation) worked with a critical understanding of energy citizenship that was grounded in state-of-the-art Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) insights. Funded under the EU Horizon 2020 programme for three years (2021-2024), EnergyPROSPECTS aimed to develop a broad understanding of energy citizenship as a policy concept, a sociotechnical imaginary, a knowing-of-governance, i.e. a social construction of desirable/normal civic agency in future energy systems.</p> <p>Countries: Belgium, Bulgaria, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Latvia, Spain, The Netherlands</p>	<p>Partner institutions: University of Galway (UG), Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB), GreenDependent Institute (GDI), Universiteit Maastricht (UM), Applied Research and Communications Fund (ARC Fund), Notre Europe – Institut Jacques Delors (JDI), University of Latvia (UL), Technische Universität Berlin (TUB), Universidade da Coruña (UDC),</p> <p>Disciplines: Geography, social psychology, innovation studies, sociology, ethnology, political sciences, science and technology studies, environmental economics, philosophy, epistemology.</p> <p>Quantified foci/approaches on structures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PESTEL Analyses of the factors impacting energy citizenship (EU, national and regional/local levels), AHP and DEMATEL use for various rankings of the EU factors and subfactors by an expert panel. See D5.1 and D5.2. - QCA Analysis of the remote and proximal conditions leading cases of energy citizenship to contribute to the democratisation of the energy system. See D4.3. - European Survey on 10.000 EU citizens (1000 in each partner countries and 10*100 in other EU countries). See D5.4.

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<p>EU 1.5° Lifestyles (2021-2025): The project analyses opportunities and barriers for the mainstreaming of lifestyles that are in line with the 1.5° climate target, with a focus on Europe. To that end, EU 1.5° Lifestyles quantifies climate and health impacts of shifting lifestyles, identifies and explores low-carbon transformative strategies for households, assesses the role of structural constraints and barriers, and analyses potential risks of lifestyles changes at the household levels as well as the interaction of such changes with welfare systems and business models. The project pursues its aims via quantitative and qualitative methods, as well as innovative participatory formats, and develops guidance for policy makers, citizens, and other stakeholders.</p> <p>Countries: The EE-MRIO analysis considers 49 countries with an emphasis on the 27 member countries of the EU. Case countries for qualitative assessments are Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Spain, and Sweden.</p>	<p>Partner institutions: Research Institute for Sustainability (RIFS) - Helmholtz Centre Potsdam, Lund University, adelphi, GreenDependentInstitute, Green Liberty, University of Leiden, University of Coruna, D-Mat, European Research Services</p> <p>Disciplines: industrial ecology, political science, economics, psychology, env. social sciences</p> <p>Quantified foci/approaches on structures: Environmentally extended multi-regional input-output analysis (EE-MRIO).</p> <p>Key publications on quantitative and structural analyses: Cap, S., A. de Koning, A. Tukker, L. Scherer. 2024. (In)Sufficiency of industrial decarbonization to reduce household carbon footprints to 1.5°C-compatible levels. <i>Sustainable Production and Consumption</i> 45: 216-227. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2023.12.031. Hirth, S., H. Kreinin, D. Fuchs, N. Blossey, P. Mamut, J. Philipp, I. Radovan, and the 1.5° Lifestyles Consortium. 2023. Barriers and Enablers of 1.5° Lifestyles: Shallow and Deep Structural Factors Shaping the Potential for Sustainable Consumption. <i>Frontiers in Sustainability</i> 4-23. https://doi.org/10.3389/frsus.2023.1014662. Kreinin, H., P. Mamut, D. Fuchs, S. Lange, S. Hirth. (forthcoming) Transformative change to 1.5°C Lifestyles and provisioning systems in Europe: The impact of enabling and hindering structures. <i>Sustainability: Science, Practice and Policy</i>. More publications and outputs are in progress. Please see onepointfivelifestyles.eu.</p>

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<p>FULFILL (Oct 2021 - Sept 2024) To combat climate change and achieve the Paris Agreement goals, political action is crucial. Societal changes are just as important. The EU-funded FULFILL project (“Fundamental decarbonisation through sufficiency by lifestyle changes”) explores the contribution of lifestyle changes and citizen engagement in decarbonising Europe and fulfilling the goals of the Paris Agreement. By examining sufficiency lifestyles, it identifies their intended and unintended consequences, enablers and barriers as structural conditions, as well as impacts on the individual/household and community/municipal level to determine routine behaviours that can lower energy demand and emissions and at the same time contribute to well-being.</p> <p>Countries: Denmark, Germany, France, Italy, Latvia and India</p>	<p>Partner institutions: Fraunhofer ISI, Inforse, Jacques Delors Institute, NegaWatt, Polimi, Wuppertal Institute, Zala Brivida</p> <p>Disciplines and perspectives: social science and humanities, techno-economic energy and climate studies.</p> <p>Quantified foci/approaches on structures from key project deliverables: Tröger, Josephine, Edouard Toulouse, Abigail Alexander-Haw, Elisabeth Dütschke, Yves Maignac, Sabine Preuß, and Adrien Toledano. Refinement of Research Design. FULFILL Deliverable D 2.3, 2022. Alexander-Haw, Abigail, Elisabeth Dütschke, Hannah Janßen, Joachim Schleich, Josephine Tröger, and Mareike Tschaut. Report on Long Term Effects of Sufficiency Lifestyles and Governance Approaches for Diffusion. FULFILL Deliverable D 3.1, 2024. Alexandre Gabert, Yves Maignac, Mathilde Djelali, Charline Dufournet, Aurore Flipo. Report on the consolidation of quantified sufficiency hypotheses in decarbonisation strategies FULFILL Deliverable D 5.3, 2024. Adrien Jacob, Nicolas Taillard. Indicators and factors for the integration of energy sufficiency in models. FULFILL Deliverable D 6.1, 2024. Available at https://fulfill-sufficiency.eu/our-research/</p>